

NANOTECHNOLOGY IN AIR POLLUTION

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Air Pollution

Abstract:

It the issue of air pollution, its classification, sources, and health impacts. It distinguishes between natural and man-made contaminants, including aerosols, dust, smoke, mist, fog, fumes, and gases. The gases section focuses on sulphur dioxide and nitrogen oxides, their sources, and health effects. The article also mentions volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and their impact on air quality and human health.

Keywords: Air pollution, Classification, Sources, Health impacts, Aerosols, Dust, Smoke, Mist, Fog, Fumes, Gases, Sulphur dioxide, Nitrogen oxides, VOCs

1.0 Definition

Air pollution means the presence in the outdoor atmosphere of one or more contaminant such as dust, fumes, gas, mist, odor, smoke or vapour in quantities, with characteristics and of durations such as to be injurious to human, plant or plant life or to property or which unreasonably interfere with the comfortable enjoyment of life and property.

1.1 Classification and characterization of air pollution:

Air pollutants can be either natural or may be the result of various activities of man like industrial operations. The industrial contaminants can be either by products of external combustion like smoke, dust and sulphur oxides or by products of internal combustion like the reactions in petrol and diesel engines. Further the emissions can be either primary pollutants or secondary pollutants. Air pollutants can be classified as follows:-

a) Natural contaminants:

The contaminants which arise naturally e.g. natural fog, pollen grains, bacteria and products of volcanic eruption. Among natural contaminants pollen grain is important. Because of wind pollination, thousands of pollen grains are librated. They are discharged into the atmosphere from weeds, grass and trees. Because of wind pollination thousands of pollen grains are liberated. Air transported pollen grains range between 10 μ and 50 μ in size, but it is also found that pollen of small size as 5 μ and as large as 100 μ in diameter one also seen contaminating air. From the point of view of pollution, air borne pollutants are significant because of the allergic responses produced in sensitive asthma or hay fever some develop bronchitis asthma and dermatitis.

b) Aerosols (particulates):

Aerosols refer to dispersion of solid or liquid particles of microscopic size in gaseous media such as dust, mist, fog or fumes. An aerosol can also be defined as a colloidal state in which dispersion medium is gas and the dispersed phase is solid or liquid. The term “aerosol” is used during the time it is suspended in the air. After it has settle either by the virtue of its weight, agglomeration or by the impact in a solid or liquid surface, the term no longer affixes. Thus particulate matter in an air pollutant only when it is an aerosol. However it is a nuisance as an aerosol (visibility reduction) and as settled or deposited matter, soiling of surface corrosions. Aerosol differs widely in terms of particle size, particle density and their importance as pollutants. Their diameter generally ranges from 0.01 μ or less up to about 100 μ .

c) Dust:

Dust is a aerosol made up of solid particles predominantly larger than those found in colloids and are capable of temporary suspension in air or other gases. They do not tend to flocculate except electrostatic forces. They also do not diffuse but settle under the influence of gravity. Crushing of organic and inorganic materials produce dust. Generally they are around 20 μ in diameter, some are smaller also. Fly ash from chimneys varies from 80 μ - 3 μ , cement varies from 150 μ - 10 μ , foundry dust from 200 μ - 1 μ . Most of the dust particles settle to the ground as dust fall, but particles 5 μ or smaller tend to form stable suspensions.

d) Smoke:

Smoke consists of finely divided particles produced by incomplete combustion consists mainly of carbon particles and other combustible materials. Generally the size of the particle is less than 1 μ . The size of coal smoke particle ranges from 0.2 μ to 0.01 μ and oil smoke particles from 1.0 μ to 0.03 μ .

e) Mist:

This term refers to the low concentration dispersion of liquid particles of larger size. In meteorology it means a light dispersion of minute water droplets suspended in the atmosphere. Natural mist particles formed from water vapour in the atmosphere are rather large, ranging from 500 μ - 40 μ in size. The particles may coalesce.

f) Fog:

Fog refers to visible aerosol in which the dispersed phase is liquid. Formation by condensation is usually implied. In meteorology it refers to dispersion of water or ice

in the atmosphere near the earth's surface reducing visibility to $\frac{1}{2}$ km. In natural fog the size of the particle ranges from 40μ - 1.0μ .

g) Fumes:

These are solid particles generated by condensation from the gaseous state, generally after volatilization from melted substances and often accompanied by a chemical reaction such as oxidation. Fumes flocculate and sometimes coalesce.

h) Gases:

The various gases which are important air contaminants are Sulphur compounds, Nitrogen compounds, Oxygen compounds, Halogen compounds, organic compounds and radioactive compounds.

Sulphur dioxide:

This is one of the principal constituents of air pollutants. The main source of sulphur dioxide is combustion of fuels, especially coal. Therefore its concentration depends upon the sulphur content of the fuel used for heating and power generation. It is a colorless gas with a characteristic sharp pungent odour. It is moderately soluble in water forming weak acidic sulphurous acid. It is oxidized slowly in air to sulphur trioxide (SO_3). In a polluted atmosphere, SO_2 reacts photochemically or catalytically with other pollutants or normal atmospheric constituents to form SO_3 , H_2SO_4 and salts of H_2SO_4 . The sulphur content of fuels varies from less than 1% for good quality anthracite to over 4% for bituminous coal. Most crude petroleum products contain less than 1% sulphur, a few contain up to 5%. During the refining process, the fuel gases contain sulphur in small quantities. About 80% of the sulphur in coal and nearly all that in liquid and gaseous fuels is found in fuel gases in the form of sulphur dioxide. The remaining sulphur in coal is present as inorganic sulphur and thus remains in the ash. In general the concentration of sulphur dioxide in fuel gases ranges from 0.05% - 0.25% and occasionally is as high as 0.4%. Another common source of sulphur dioxide in the atmosphere is metallurgical operations. Many ores like Zinc, Copper and Lead are primarily sulphides. During the smelting of these ores, sulphur dioxide is evolved in stack concentrations of 5% - 10%. The other source of SO_2 into the atmosphere are sulphuric acid plants and paper manufacturing plants. The open burning of refuse and in municipal incinerators also contribute some amount of sulphur dioxide to the atmosphere.

Oxides of Nitrogen:

It is known that oxides of nitrogen are the second most abundant atmospheric contaminants in many cities. The highest concentration of nitrogen oxides in gaseous emissions occur in effluents from industries where nitric acid is produced or used in chemical reactions. The next highest concentration is in automobile exhausts. Effluents from power plants, low heat burners

and furnaces also produce certain amount of nitrogen oxides as pollutants. Out of the different oxides of nitrogen only nitrogen oxide and nitrogen dioxide are classified as

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of nitrogen only nitrogen oxide and nitrogen dioxide are classified as pollutants. In atmospheric analysis they are usually reported as total oxides of nitrogen or NO_x . In chemical industry NO_x is absorbed and recovered.

Carbon monoxide:

It is an odourless and colourless gas which has its major origin in the incomplete combustion of carbonaceous materials. It is a highly poisonous gas and is generally classified as an asphyxiant. The chief source of carbon monoxide in the atmosphere is combustion especially due to automobile exhausts. Although certain industrial operations such as electric and blast furnace, some petroleum refining operations, gas manufacturing plants and coal mine are potential contributors of carbon monoxide in to the atmosphere, automobile exhausts are by far the most important source.

VARIOUS HEALTH POLLUTION DUE TO AIR POLLUTION:

1. Eye irritation.
2. Throat and nose irritation.
3. Irritation of the respiratory tract.
4. Gases like H_2S , NH_3 and mercaptans cause odour nuisance event at low concentrations.
5. Increase in mortality rate and morbidity rate.
6. A variety of particulates particularly pollens, initiate asthmatic attacks.
7. Chronic pulmonary diseases like bronchitis and asthma are aggravated by a high concentration of SO_2 , NO_2 , particulate matter and PCS.
8. CO combines with the hemoglobin in the blood and consequently increases stress on those suffering from cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases.
9. Hydrogen fluoride causes diseases of the bone (fluorosis) and degradation of teeth.
10. Carcinogenic agents cause cancer.
11. Dust particles like silica, asbestos present in the dust cause diseases like silicosis and asbestosis, which causes respiratory diseases.
12. Lung poisoning may be caused due to inhaling certain heavy metals like lead.

Specific pollutants affecting human health :

Sulphur dioxide:

Sulphur dioxide is an irritant which affects the mucous membranes when inhaled under certain conditions some of the air borne SO_2 is oxidized to SO_3 . Each these two gases in the

presence of water vapours form sulphurous and sulphuric acid respectively and can cause severe bronchospasms at respectively low levels of concentrations.

Carbon monoxide:

CO has a strong affinity for combining with hemoglobin to form carboxy hemoglobin. This reduces the ability of hemoglobin to carry oxygen to the body tissues. CO has about two hundred times the affinity of oxygen for attaching to hemoglobin. Carbon monoxides also effect nervous system. It can also cause heart attacks.

Oxides of nitrogen:

Of the seven oxides of nitrogen known to exist in the ambient air, only two are thought to effect human health (nitric oxide and nitric dioxide). It is estimated that eye and nasal irritation and pulmonary discomfort will be observed after exposure to the oxides of nitrogen. presence of water vapours form sulphurous and sulphuric acid respectively and can cause severe bronchospasms at respectively low levels of concentrations.

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ARTICLE REVIEW

GOLD NANOPARTICLES IN MANGANESE OXIDE CLEANS VOCs FROM AIR

In addition to nitrogen oxides and sulfur oxides, many volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in air contribute to smog and high ozone levels, as well as potentially damaging human health. Clean air laws are thus rightly continuing to become stricter. Most modern air purification systems are based on photocatalysts, adsorbents such as activated charcoal, or ozonolysis. However, these classic systems are not particularly good at breaking down organic pollutants at room temperature. Japanese researchers have now developed a new material that very effectively removes VOCs as well as nitrogen and sulfur oxides from air at room temperature. As they report in the journal *Angewandte Chemie*, their system involves a highly porous manganese oxide with gold nanoparticles grown into it. To prove the effectiveness of their new catalyst, the research team headed by Anil K. Sinha at the Toyota Central R&D Labs carried out tests with acetaldehyde, toluene, and hexane. These three major components of organic air pollution play a role indoors as well as out. All three of these pollutants were very effectively removed from air and degraded by the catalyst—significantly better than with conventional catalyst systems.

One secret to the success of this new material is the extremely large inner surface area of the porous manganese oxide, which is higher than all previously known manganese oxide compounds. This large surface area offers the volatile molecules a large number of adsorption sites. Moreover, the adsorbed pollutants are very effectively broken down. There is clearly plenty of oxygen available for oxidation processes within the manganese oxide lattice. Degradation on the surface is highly effective because free radicals are present there. Presumably, oxygen from air dissociates on the gold surface to replace the consumed oxygen atoms in the lattice structure. This process only works if the material is produced in a very specific manner. The gold must be deposited onto the manganese oxide by means of vacuum UV laser ablation. In this technique, a gold surface is irradiated with a special laser, which dislodges gold particles through evaporation. These gold particles have unusually high energy, which allows them to drive relatively deep into the surface of the manganese oxide. This process is the only way to induce sufficiently strong interactions between the little clumps of gold and the manganese oxide support.[1]

SYNTHETIC GENE LIKE CRYSTALS FOR CARBON

DIOXIDE CAPTURE

UCLA chemists report creating a synthetic "gene" that could capture heat trapping carbon dioxide emissions, which contribute to global warming, rising sea levels and the increased acidity of oceans.

The research appears in Feb.12 issue of the journal Science.

UCLA chemistry and biochemistry professor Omar M. Yaghi said that they have created three dimensional, synthetic DNA like crystals. Professor Yaghi is a member of the California Nanosystems Institute (CNSI) at UCLA and the UCLA- Department of Energy Institute of Genomics and proteomics. They have taken organic and inorganic units and combined them into a synthetic crystal which codes information in a DNA- like manner. It is by no means as sophisticated as DNA, but it is certainly new in chemistry and materials science.

The discovery could lead to cleaner energy, including technology that factories and cars can use to capture carbon dioxide before it reaches the atmosphere.

It will be important for potentially getting to viable carbon dioxide- capture material with ultra high selectivity. Professor Yaghi, who holds UCLA's Irving and Jean Stone Chair in Physical Sciences and is director of the CNSI's Centre for Reticular Chemistry said that they could create a material that can convert carbon dioxide into a fuel or a material that can separate carbon dioxide with greater efficiency.

The research was federally funded by the U.S Department of Energy's Office of basic Energy Sciences. The lead author is Hexiang "DJ" Deng, a UCLA graduate student of chemistry and biochemistry who works in Yaghi's laboratory.

DNA is a beautiful molecule that has a way to code for information, How to code information in a crystal in the same way that DNA does? DJ and Professor Yaghi have figured out a way to do this. The sequence of organic functionalities that decorates the pores of the crystals is most certainly a unique code.

DJ has illustrated that one member of a series of materials he has made has 400 percent better performance in carbon dioxide capture than on that does not have the same code.

In the early 1990s, Yaghi invented a class of materials called metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), sometimes described as crystal sponges, in which he can change the components

nearly at will. MOFs have pores - openings on the nanoscale in which Yaghi and his colleagues can store gases that are usually difficult to store and transport. Molecules can go in and out of the pores unobstructed. Yaghi and his research team have made thousands of MOFs.

They have created crystals of metal organic frameworks in which the sequence of multiple functionalities of varying kind and ratios acts as a synthetic gene, with these multivariate MOFs, they have figured out a way to incorporate controlled complexity, which biology operates on, in asynthetic crystal- taking synthetic crystals to a new level of performance.

This can be a boon for energy related and other industrial application, such as conversion of gases and liquids like carbon dioxide to fuel, or water to hydrogen, among many others.

Yaghi has been collaborating with his former UCLA chemistry colleague and former CNSI director SirJ.Fraser Stoddart on how to take concepts from biology and incorporate them into a synthetic material.

The materials they are creating will introduce a new class of structures that have controlled complexity, chemists and material scientists are now able to ask new questions we have never asked before, also new tools for characterizing the sequence and deciphering the codes within the crystals will have to be developed.

Carbon dioxide is polluting Earth's atmosphere and damaging coral reefs and marine life impacts that are irreversible in our lifetime.

Co-authors on the study are Christian Dooran and Hiroyasu Furukawa , UCLA postdoctoral scholars in Yaghi's laboratory,Ricardo Feriera, a UCLA visiting undergraduate. John Towne, a former Ucla undergraduate, Carolyn Knobler , a research associate in Yaghi's laboratory, and Bo Wang, a UCLA postdoctoral scholar in Yaghi's laboratory.[2]

A LOW COST CATALYST PREPARATION

A research group led by Charles Lyman, professor of materials science and engineering, has developed catalysts that convert the harmful nitrogen oxides emitted from coal- and gas-fired power plants to nitrogen and water vapor. Unlike other methods of converting nitrogen oxides (NO_x), the low-cost nanoparticle-based catalysts developed by Lyman's group do not use ammonia. NO_x is a generic term for nitrogen oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The oxides, which are responsible for smog and acid rain, are produced when nitrogen and oxygen react in the air during combustion, especially at high temperatures.

The use of catalysts for pollution control in power plants is not new. A technique called selective catalytic reduction (SCR) can convert 95 percent of NO_x to nitrogen and water—but with a catch. Conventional SCR requires another toxic gas, ammonia, to carry out the reduction, in addition, these catalysts only perform well at high temperatures.

Finding the best preparation technique

Lyman and Herman sought first to improve the performance of a platinum-rhodium nanoparticle-based catalyst that uses hydrogen, rather than ammonia, as a reducing agent. This catalyst works at much lower temperatures. Choosing the correct catalyst preparation procedure was critical to ensuring that all these criteria were met. To obtain the desired microstructure, researchers sequentially impregnated an alumina support with aqueous solutions of platinum and rhodium chlorides. Then they applied a series of thermal treatments to convert the metal chlorides into active bimetallic nanoparticles. Ph.D candidate Dimick said that this procedure was chosen so that the desired microstructure would be achieved under reaction conditions.

When the researchers examined the prepared catalysts with Lehigh's high-resolution aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscope, they found nanoparticles with an average diameter of 2 nanometers (nm) well-dispersed on the alumina support. One nm is one billionth of a meter. In-situ Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy revealed that the N-O chemical bond in a catalyst containing 5-percent rhodium was broken as soon as the molecule made contact with the nanoparticle. In a catalyst of 10-percent rhodium, however, the NO molecules tended to adhere to clusters of rhodium atoms present on the surface, which could potentially inhibit the desired reaction. Catalyst performance data also showed that the catalyst containing only 5-percent rhodium exhibited a much higher activity.

Cobalt's low-cost advantage

Rhodium, however, is rare and expensive. It now trades at around \$2,400 per troy ounce after exceeding \$10,000 in 2008. To reduce NO_x emissions more cheaply, the researchers turned to cobalt, which is 900 times less expensive than rhodium. Cobalt is also capable of breaking the N-O bond, it forms a solid solution with platinum at low concentrations and finds its way to the surface of a nanoparticle under reaction conditions. The preparation of cobalt-platinum catalysts is almost identical to that of rhodium-platinum. The researchers merely substituted metal nitrates for chlorides. While all catalysts containing less than 5 percent cobalt were found to be capable of reducing NO_x to nitrogen and water vapor, the 2-percent cobalt catalyst performed best. In-situ FTIR spectroscopy revealed that the 2 percent catalyst was the only one capable of immediately breaking the N-O bond. The same methodology has now been applied to a nickel-platinum catalyst system with equally promising results.[3]

CONVERTING CO₂ INTO CARBON NANOTUBES

In 2015, researchers at George Washington University proposed a method for transforming CO₂ emissions into carbon nano tubes (CNTs). When applied to power plants, the technology could completely eliminate the power plants CO₂ emissions while simultaneously producing a valuable product that is used for a variety of applications, including batteries, consumer electronics, airplanes and athletic equipment. The technology can work with almost any kind of power plant, but the researchers specifically investigated its application for combined cycle(CC) natural gas power plants, which are the most efficient kind of electrical power plant yet still emit massive amounts of CO₂. The idea is to add a molten lithium carbonate electrolyzer to a conventional CC plant, creating a CC carbon nanofiber(CC CNF) plant. Using electrolysis the same technology that splits water to produce hydrogen, the system applies a voltage to split CO₂ into oxygen gas and solid carbon nanofibers. Adding in small quantities of nickel causes the carbon nanofibers to be hollow, forming CNTs.

To make sure that the idea isn't too good to be true, in a new study the same researchers have performed a thermodynamic assessment of the proposed CC CNF plant. They found that the concept is economically feasible and even improves the power plant's energy efficiency. The technology incentivizes carbon dioxide removal by transforming this greenhouse gas into a valuable product to ameliorate the impact of climate change. Stuart Licht, a chemistry professor at George Washington University and leader of the study, told *Phys.org* that the production of CNTs will actually be more profitable for fossil fuel power plants than making power, and this should incentivize the transition to a renewable, sustainable society. CNTs have over twenty times the strength of steel or aluminium and are lower weight, and we hope that the CNTs will provide a complete replacement for the trillion dollar steel and aluminium market. CNTs are useful in nanoelectronics and new medicine delivery systems, and are already being used in textiles [such as bullet-proof clothing].

The researchers' assessment shows that, for every metric ton of methane fuel consumed, a conventional CC power plant produces \$909 of electricity and emits 2.74 tons of CO₂. In contrast, the proposed CC CNF plant would produce about \$835 of electricity, which is about 8% less than the CC plant. But the CC CNF plant would also produce about 0.75 tons of CNTs, which is worth an estimated \$225,000 and emits no CO₂. In other words, the small decrease in power output is more than compensated for by the highly valuable carbon nanofibers and nanotubes that could be produced. This is mainly because industrial-grade carbon nanotubes are such an expensive commodity, which currently cost about \$300,000/ton to produce using methods available today. Using the new method, the

researchers estimate that it would cost just \$2000/ton to produce CNTs-less than 1% of current production costs.

The researchers hope that this large profit potential will make the technology seem like an obvious choice. Since CNTs are about 10,000 times more valuable than carbon tax credits(which are roughly \$30/ton), the researchers predict that CNT production will offer a greater incentive for the energy industry to reduce carbon emissions than carbon tax credits offer. Even though the value of CNTs would likely decrease in the future since they can be produced much more easily and cheaply using this new method, that would simply spread part of the economic benefit to other industries. Lower CNT prices would spur CNT market growth and positively impact the many industries that use them, including the automobile, airline and wind turbine industries. The researchers assessment also shows that the CC CNF plants make sense from a thermodynamic perspective when compared to conventional CC plants with and without carbon sequestration, as well as conventional coal plants.

Even though the CC CNF plants would produce somewhat less electricity than the other types of plants, they would do so at a higher efficiency. The improved efficiency is due to heat energy gained in several areas that could be recycled back into the steam turbines. The heat energy comes, for instance, from the energy produced from chemical reactions with lithium oxide; the energy gained from cooling the carbon and oxygen products; the energy gained from burning the natural gas with a mix of pure oxygen and air (splitting the CO₂ releases pure oxygen as well CNTs); the energy saved from preventing CO₂ emissions; and the energy gained by capturing CO₂ at a much higher temperature than the temperatures at which CC plants with carbon sequestration operate. And unlike carbon capture technologies, energy is not need to store the CO₂ as a waste material, since instead it is converted to a valuable product. [4]

HEALTH IMPACTS OF NANO PARTICLES

New groundbreaking research has found that exposure to nanoparticles can have a serious impact on health, linking it to rheumatoid arthritis and the development of other serious autoimmune diseases. The findings have health and safety implications for the manufacture, use and ultimate disposal of nanotechnology products and materials. They also identified new cellular targets for the development of potential drug therapies in combating the development of autoimmune diseases. Environmental pollution including carbon particles emitted by car exhaust, smoking and long term inhalation of dust of various origins have been recognized as risk factors causing inflammation of the lungs. The link between smoking and autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis has also been established. This new research now raises serious concerns in relation to similar risks caused by nanotechnology products which if not handled appropriately may contribute to the generation of new types of airborne pollutants causing risks to global health. In their research the Nanomedicine and Molecular Imaging team at Trinity College Dublin's School of Medicine led by Professor of Molecular Medicine, Yuri Volkov investigated whether there was a common underlying mechanism contributing to the development of autoimmune diseases in human cells following their exposure to a wide range of nanoparticles containing different physical and chemical properties.

The scientists applied a wide range of nanomaterials including ultrafine carbon black, carbon nanotubes and silicone dioxide particles of different sizes, ranging from 20 to 400 nanometers, to human cells derived from the lining of the airway passages, and to the cells of so called phagocytic origin - those cells that are most frequently exposed to the inhaled foreign particles or are tasked with cleaning up our body from them. At the same time, collaborating researchers from the Health Effects Laboratory Division, National Institute for Occupational Safety & Health (Morgantown, WV, USA) have conducted the studies in mice exposed to chronic inhalation of air contaminated with single walled carbon nanotubes. The result was convincing: all types of nanoparticles in both the TCD and US study were causing an identical response in human cells and in the lungs of mice, manifesting in the specific transformation of the amino acid arginine into the molecule called citrulline which can lead to the development of autoimmune conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis. In the transformation of citrulline, human proteins which incorporate this modified amino acid as building blocks, can no longer function properly and are subject to destruction and elimination by the bodily defense system. Once programmed to get rid of citrullinated proteins, the immune system can start attacking its own tissues and organs, thereby causing the autoimmune processes which may result in rheumatoid arthritis.

The research establishes a clear link between autoimmune diseases and nanoparticles. Preventing or interfering with the resulting citrullination process looks therefore as a promising target for the development of future preventative and therapeutic approaches in rheumatoid arthritis and possibly other autoimmune conditions.[5]

NANO SENSORS

Sensors can be developed by using the properties of matter at nano dimensions. In such devices, the functional units will be nano entities though the material itself may not be nano in dimension. The properties of nanomaterials such as the large surface to volume ratio and photophysical properties will be used in generating a signal when analyte molecules interact with it. Several such sensors have been developed.

Sensor: the term 'sensor' can be referred to any device that uses an active chemical species or component that generates a signal in presence of an analyte molecule. The signal, in turn, is used either directly or after suitable amplification to trigger a suitable detector.

There are three essential components of a sensor device:

1 The responding element, which recognizes the presence of the analyte species and generates a signal. This is the principal component which 'sees' the molecule, ion or process.

In general, a sensor element has to satisfy certain requirements like:

- a) It should be capable of detailing the analyte in a qualitative and quantitative manner.
- b) It should be able to detect even very small amounts of the analyte.
- c) The signal it generates should be reproducible. This implies that the sensor should not have a strong affinity for the analyte, in which case the sensor will be passivated with the analyte after some time, leading to an irreproducible response. The affinity should be optimal so that the analyte is disengaged from the sensor after a short interaction time period, during which the sensor transfers its response to the next stage.
- d) The sensor should be very selective and specific in its response towards a target molecule.

2 An amplifier, which receives the signal of the sensor as an input and amplifies it to a level that is acceptable for processing by the detector, and

3 A detector, which receives the output of the amplifier as an input and converts it, in a pre-programmed manner, to a parameter which represents either the analyte species or its concentration or both. In most cases, the detector is equipped with a feedback control through which it signals to the sensor that the input has been received and processed. This acts as a trigger for the sensor to release the analyte molecule. This process causes an induction time

period during which the sensor is not available for response. Therefore, the induction time period should be as small as possible.

4.1 NANOSCALE ORGANIZATION FOR SENSORS

A translation of liquid state properties to solid state is of utmost importance in the development of sensors and devices. One of the major hurdles in achieving this is that this transfer has to be done without altering the liquid phase properties. In this process, assembling of the particles and an enhanced ordering have to be achieved to enable uniform and isotropic detection protocol. A variety of substrates are employed for carrying the nanoparticles, with the most common among them being metals like Au, Pt, etc. and conducting glass substrates. Metallic surfaces are utilized for the spectroscopic probing of the molecules using Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) that gives information about the alignment and the nature of interaction existing between the molecule and metal. On the other hand, transparent conducting glass substrates lend themselves to a variety of electrical and microscopic (as well as spectroscopic) probing, besides being technologically more attractive. Many methods are used to achieve the assembly and further ordering of the nanoparticles.

4.2 SELF ASSEMBLY

This is one of the most widely used and simplest methods of organizing nanoparticles onto substrates. Normally, this method is adopted for attaching the nanoparticles (using metallic) on surfaces like conducting glass or metal films. The substrate is first cleaned and activated suitably, with the process depending on the nature of the substrate and the nanoparticles. The surface is made either hydrophobic or hydrophilic as is necessitated by the type of the nanoparticle. In the case of metallic substrates, the cleaned surface might be sufficiently active for the attachment of the nanoparticles. Otherwise, the activated surface is functionalized with anchor molecules to facilitate the binding of the nanoparticles. These anchor molecules are characterized by the presence of certain functional groups to which the nanoparticles will adhere. A silane containing thiol or amino functional group, capable of forming a covalent link, is best suited for the adhesion of gold nanoparticles. The type and extent of functionalization is controlled by the nature of application for which it is fabricated. For example, for electrochemical studies, a thick polymeric layer of alkoxy silane will hinder the transport of ions and electrons between the nanoparticles and the substrate.

The assembly thus achieved is referred to as 'self assembled layer' (SAL). More specifically, if a single monolayer adsorption is achieved, it is known as a 'self assembled monolayer' (SAM). This is more relevant with respect to the organization of molecules on a metal or

nanoparticle surface. It is thus known as there is no external driving force other than the mutual affinity between the nanoparticles and the functional groups on the substrate. This plays a crucial role in deciding the specificity of the nanoparticles that goes on to form the SAL and SAM.

4.3 TEMPLATE METHOD

One of the main disadvantages of the self assembly method is its sensitivity in terms of external parameters. It is almost impossible to obtain two similarly arranged surfaces, with the adhesion and the organization depending on various factors like solvent, concentrations, temperature, type of substrate, and so on. In fact, even on a given surface, there is a high possibility of the existence of a coverage gradient, leading to inconsistency in results.

One way to overcome this is to fabricate a template with regions wherein the possibility of the adsorption of a nanoparticle is artificially enhanced. The most common example is the use of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) to create the necessary patterns on the substrate. On activating the plate, the portions containing the PMMA remain passive and hence the nanoparticles are not able to bind to the substrates at those places. Conversely, if a suitably charged microstructure polymer is chosen, instead of PMMA, the nanoparticles adhere on the substrate to the regions containing the polymer. An example in this case would be the patterning of Pd nanoparticles using a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) template.

An advancement of this technique is the use of light to create the patterns on a functionalized surface. The salinization is done with a suitable group such as amine or thiol in the case of gold nanoparticles. The substrate is then exposed to light in certain areas leading to oxidation of the groups. Exposure to nanoparticles makes the light exposed regions passive.

Scheme 12.3: Some of the methods of template-assisted organization of nanoparticles.

template method to bind nanoparticles to substrates

4.4 BIOLOGICAL ASSEMBLING

Complimentary DNA strands can be used to self assemble nanoparticles in the form of wires and helical structures. Going further, the recent trend has been to immobilize DNA, either as oligonucleotides or as duplex strands, on substrates. This is followed by the deposition of nanoparticles to create specific patterns. These patterns arise due to the enhanced affinity of the nanoparticles towards certain residues of DNA. For example, it has been established that DNA strands can act as stabilizers for Cds nanoparticles and that the content of adenine influences its morphology and photophysical properties. Accordingly, duplex DNA are immobilized on substrates and Cd^{2+} ions are assembled on it, with high degree of specificity. Following exposure to H_2S , these are converted into CdS nanoparticles. These methodologies offer a high degree of flexibility in generating various patterns of arrangement.

The recognition based organizational ability of biomolecules has led to their qualification as ideal candidates for organizing and patterning nanoparticles. One of the strategies adopted for generating nanoparticle arrangements is through the interaction between antigens and antibody. Besides their high specificity, these interactions are chemically stable and offer a wide range of equilibrium constants, thereby allowing fine control over the organizational behavior and pattern. The most commonly exploited biomolecule for achieving this is the biotin-sav combination.

Conclusion

After successful completion of the self study, the following conclusions, orienting towards Programme Outcomes may be made.

PO No.	PO	PO achievement during the <u>self study</u>
PO1	ENGINEERING KNOWLEDGE	Studying about nanotechnology used in air pollution control has increased the knowledge related to nanotechnology
PO2	PROBLEM ANALYSIS	The tools used in combating air pollution range widely, many elements are used at nano scale to trap air pollutants
PO3	DESIGN/DEVELOPMENT OF SOLUTIONS	Different elements are used at nanoscale to combat air pollution
PO4	CONDUCT INVESTIGATIONS OF COMPLEX PROBLEMS	<u>Journal</u> studies on air pollution show that nanotechnology is effective and cheap
PO5	MODERN TOOL USAGE	Nano materials are used of different elements to trap air pollutants
PO6	THE ENGINEER AND SOCIETY	I Importance of project for the need of the society is explained and the role and responsibility of Civil Engineer to cater to the need of society was highlighted.
PO7	ENVIROMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY	Reduction of greenhouse gases is a huge step towards reduction of global warming
PO8	ETHICS	Professional ethics is an integral part of any project. At all the stages of project, adhering to the <u>codal provisions and standards</u> is highlighted.
PO9	INDIVIDUAL AND TEAM WORK	This <u>self study</u> project was an individual effort to study on nanotechnology used in combating air pollution
PO10	COMMUNICATION	Preparation of project report, communicating instructions at site either orally or in written communication is most important for successful completion of project work. How the communications were done during project execution is explained with an example of written communications ledger maintained.
PO11	PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE	Application of project management tool for effective project management and financial aspect is explained How to execute a given work, prepare financial <u>schedule for the funds</u> by both State and Central Government was brought in.
PO12	LIFE LONG LEARNING	Updating the knowledge of latest construction technology, use of <u>modern tools and equipments</u> is essential for the employees to <u>servive</u> in the field. Hence, an employee /Civil Engineer is required to upgrade his skills time to time to be successful in the industry.

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